

Properties of Activated Sugar Charcoal Coated with Various Substances. Part I. Liberation of Acid and Alkali by the Action of Neutral Salts in Relation to the Surface Charge.

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Surfaces of charcoal activated at moderate temperatures up to about 500° appears to contain acidic substances (Kolthoff, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1932, **54**, 4473). The formation of different types of oxides on the surface has been assumed at different temperatures (Schilov and co-workers, *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1930, **148**, 233; *ibid.*, 1930, **149**, 211). It has also been suggested (Ockrent, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1934, **291**) that the properties of activated charcoal are mainly the result of an activated layer of water molecules on the surface. A relationship appears to exist between the primarily adsorbed ions on the surface and its charge, the liberation of acid or alkali by neutral salts of strong acids and bases, and the adsorption of strong acids and strong bases (Roychoudhury, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1931, **8**, 433; Roychoudhury and Mukherjee, *Kolloid Z.*, 1931, **57**, 302; *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1931, **157**, 435). In the light of these considerations experiments were undertaken to treat activated sugar charcoal with different substances so as to produce surface coats, or, primarily adsorbed layers of known nature and to study their properties with respect to the factors just mentioned. It will be seen below that coats produced by organic acids give surfaces which have a negative charge and simultaneously contain hydrogen ions replaceable with ease by neutral alkali or alkaline earth salts. Treatment with amines on the other hand favours the formation of surfaces having weaker negative charge and easily replaceable hydroxyl ions or showing a decrease in the amount of replaceable hydrogen ions. Several amino-acids, mercaptan, ketones and an aldehyde have also been used.

EXPERIMENTAL.

The sugar charcoal X (for preparation see the paper to be communicated by Acharya and Ray to *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*) used as a basis for the coats was obtained by the activation of pure sugar charcoal at 600° for 6 hours in air at 1 mm. of Hg. It had a weak

negative charge in contact with water. The electro-osmotic rates were determined in the manner used by Roychoudhury (*loc. cit.*).

The sample Y (*vide* Table XIV) was iso-electric with water (null charcoal) and was obtained by further activating X at 600° for another 4 hours under the same pressure of air. On treatment with a neutral electrolyte, Y liberated slight traces of alkali, while X liberated small quantities of acid.

2 G. of the activated charcoal X were kept in contact for 24 hours with 10 c.c. alcoholic solutions containing 0.02 g. of the organic substance. The alcohol was then evaporated and the charcoal dried in a silica crucible on a water-bath. The charcoal thus treated was further activated in some cases. The various resulting charcoals were divided into two parts, A and B.

'A' was again divided into about two equal parts, A₁ and A₂ in two cleansed, steamed and dried Jena glass bottles. 40 C.c. of conductivity water and 40 c.c. of the electrolyte solution were added respectively to A₁ and A₂. The mixtures were shaken and kept in contact for 24 hours. The upper liquid was separated by means of a powerful centrifuge and the p_H values of the supernatant liquid were determined (a) by indicators using Hellige's immersion colorimeter, and (b) also by the quinhydrone electrode. The p_H values measured by these methods are given respectively under M₁ and M₂ in the table. The following indicators have been used (*cf.* Clark, "Determination of Hydrogen Ions", 1928, pp. 93-94).

I. Bromophenol blue p_H range 3.0-4.6; p_K 3.98. II. Methyl red, 4.2-6.3; p_K 5.0. III. Bromocresol purple, 5.2-6.8; p_K 6.3. IV. Bromothymol blue 6.0-7.6, p_K 7.0. The salt effect of the indicators are I. (-0.28) - (-0.35), II. (-0.04) - (+0.10), III. (-0.25) - (-0.26) and IV. (-0.17) - (-0.19) according to different authors for the concentrations of salt used (Clark, *loc. cit.*, p. 181).

Indicator readings have been compared in a number of cases with those with the quinhydrone electrode, the difference in the two sets of values seems to be negligible. Where two indicators could be used for the same p_H determination, the difference is small (*e.g.*, p_H of an HCl solution by I, 4.43 and by II, 4.55) but the difference between values obtained with III and IV is appreciable for poorly buffered or unbuffered solutions (*e.g.*, p_H of a sample of conductivity water by III, 5.64 and by IV, 6.42).

'B' was washed repeatedly with conductivity water till the p_H of the supernatant liquid was about 6. The charcoal was then dried

in a silica crucible on a water-bath and divided into two equal parts B_1 and B_2 which were treated respectively as A_1 and A_2 .

The p_n of the conductivity water (6.42 with indicator IV), the pure electrolyte solutions and the same electrolyte solution kept in contact with the starting samples X and Y were also determined* under identical conditions.

Normal concentrations of the electrolytes were employed unless otherwise stated.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS.

TABLE I.

Charge measurements.

Treatment of charcoal.	Rate of electro-osmosis. (Movement of the air bubble in three minutes.)
1. X in contact with water	-2.5 cm.
1(a). X_1 , obtained by coating X with palmitic acid, in contact with water	-12.7 cm.
1(b). X_1 and N/10,000 KCl solution	-0.4 cm.
2. Z, prepared as X but activated in air at a pressure of 4 mm. of Hg. in contact with water.	-3.8 cm.
2(a). Z_1 obtained by coating Z with palmitic acid, in contact with water.	-13.0 cm.
2(b). Z_1 and N/10,000 solutions of the following electrolytes.	
I. KCl	-0.8 cm.
II. NaCl	-1.9 cm.
III. LiCl	-4.3 cm.
IV. BaCl ₂	-9.2 cm.

It will be seen that on being coated with an insoluble organic acid the negative charge of the charcoal surface increases, which again diminishes on being treated with neutral salt solutions and that the capacity of the cations to diminish the surface charge of the charcoal lies in the order $K > Na > Li > Ba$.

* With indicator IV the following values were obtained: N-KCl, $p_n = 6.28$, N-KCl in contact with charcoal for sample X, $p_n = 6.22$, for sample Y, $p_n = 6.32$.

According to Mukherjee (*Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1921, 16, 103; *Phil. Mag.*, 1922, vi, 44, 321; *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 2, 219; *Kolloid Z.*, 1929, 49, 362) this negative charge shows that a primarily adsorbed anion layer is present on the surfaces and H⁺-ions are most likely to be held in the neighbourhood of the surface of the charcoal by electrostatic attraction. Such of these H⁺-ions as are present on the liquid side of the double layer are mobile and are easily replaceable by cations from neutral salt solutions. The different cations should have the power of liberating H⁺-ions indicated by their capacity to diminish the negative charge on the surface. This expectation is confirmed by the following observations with charcoal coated with palmitic, stearic, lauric and myristic acids which have similar properties.

TABLE II.

Palmitic acid coat.

Electrolyte.	C ₁ *		A ₁ .	A ₂ .		Difference in p _n unit. (C ₁ -A ₂).
	M ₁ .	M ₂ .	M ₁ .	M ₁ .	M ₂ .	
KCl	6.28	6.25	5.19	4.01	4.01	2.27 (acid)
NaCl	6.39		„	4.28		2.11
LiCl	6.70		„	4.85	4.83	1.85
RbCl	5.75		„	4.20		1.55
SrCl ₂	6.23		„	5.28		0.95
BaCl ₂	6.25		„	5.58		0.67

TABLE III.

Stearic acid coat.

Electrolyte.	C ₁ .	A ₁ .	A ₂ .		Difference in p _n unit. (C ₁ -A ₂).
	M ₁ .	M ₁ .	M ₁ .	M ₂ .	
KCl	6.28	5.09	4.19		2.09 (acid)
NaCl	6.39	„	4.50	4.50	1.89
LiCl	6.70	„	5.05		1.65
RbCl	5.75	„	4.31		1.44
SrCl ₂	6.23	„	5.85		0.38
BaCl ₂	6.25	„	6.00		0.25

* C₁ indicates the p_n values of the pure electrolyte solution.

TABLE IV.

Lauric acid coat.

Electrolyte.	C ₁ .	A ₁ .	A ₂ .		Difference in p_n unit..
	M ₁ .	M ₁ .	M ₁ .	M ₂ .	
KCl	6.28	5.28	4.20	4.18	2.08 (acid)
NaCl	6.39	„	4.55		1.84
LiCl	6.70	„	5.05		1.65
RbCl	5.75	„	4.37		1.38
SrCl ₂	6.23	„	5.39		0.84
BaCl ₂	6.25	„	5.45		0.80

TABLE V.

Myristic acid coat.

Electrolyte.	C ₁ .	A ₁ .	A ₂ .		Difference in p_n unit.
	M ₁ .	M ₁ .	M ₁ .	M ₂ .	
KCl	6.28	5.47	4.22	4.20	2.06 (acid)
NaCl	6.39	„	4.47		1.92
LiCl	6.70	„	5.26		1.44
RbCl	5.75	„	4.37		1.38
SrCl ₂	6.23	„	5.39		0.84
BaCl ₂	6.25	„	5.70	5.65	0.45

The difference in p_n diminishes in the order K > Na > Li > Rb > Sr > Ba in agreement with the order K > Na > Li > Ba for the effect of these ions on the electric charge.

The order is, however, different from the order of valency and mobility deduced by Mukherjee (*loc. cit.*) from theoretical considerations, which holds good for a large number of systems.

Recently Wiegner (*Trans. Third Inter. Cong. Soil Sci.*, 1935, 3, 5) has shown from extensive measurements that the departure from the theoretical series in the cases investigated by him and his co-workers arises out of the ultraporous structure (*cf.* Herbst, *Biochem. Z.*, 1921, 118, 204; Dubinin, *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1930, 150, 145; Bell and Philip, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 1164) and the consequent differences in

the accessibility of different parts of the surface which is determined by the size of the ions. He finds (*loc. cit.*) that the larger the radius of the ion, the less is the amount of cation exchanged. In addition the intensity of the adsorption which depends on the free energy of the formation of the ion pair formed by the primarily and electrically adsorbed ions (Mukherjee, *loc. cit.*) requires to be considered. The surface may also have both cations and anions in the primarily adsorbed layer. It appears, however, that the mobility and the size of the hydrated cation are the main factors responsible for the observed series. According to Hevesey (*Kolloid Z.*, 1917, 21, 130) electrolytic ions are surrounded by an envelope of water of a thickness such that they attain more or less the same potential on their periphery. Divalent ions are, therefore, liable to have a larger diameter than univalent ions. For ions with the same valency the mobility would vary inversely as the size of the ions. If these premises be true, the series $Rb > K > Na > Li > Ba > Sr$ would result. The position of rubidium and strontium does not agree with this series.

In view of the greatest effect of KCl, this electrolyte has been used in the succeeding investigations on the comparative effects of coatings with different organic acids.

TABLE VI.

Coat of	A ₁ .		A ₂ .		Difference in β_{21} unit.
	M ₁ .	M ₂ .	M ₁ .	M ₂ .	
Lauric acid	5.28	5.28	4.01	3.99	1.27 (acid)
Myristic "	5.47		4.15		1.32 "
Palmitic "	5.19	5.19	4.01	3.99	1.18 "
Stearic "	5.09		3.92		1.17 "
Hippuric "	4.70		3.77		0.93 "
Oleic "	5.53	5.53	3.67	3.67	1.86 "
Amino-salicylic "	4.15		3.60		0.55 "
Amino-benzoic "	4.33		3.50		0.83 "
Cinnamic "	4.43		3.73		0.70 "

PROPERTIES OF ACTIVATED SUGAR CHARCOAL, ETC. 729

The different acids appear to produce coatings with easily replaceable hydrogen ions of comparable amounts. The p_n of the water in contact with charcoal (A_1 values) show wide variations. The samples were, therefore, washed and the B values (*vide* experimental section) were obtained.

TABLE VII.

Sample X.

Coat of	B_1		B_2		Difference in p_n unit
	M_1	M_2	M_1	M_2	
Lauric acid	6.15	6.14	4.26	4.21	1.89 (acid)
Myristic "	6.20		4.10		2.10 "
Palmitic "	6.00	6.10	3.87	3.87	2.13 "
Stearic "	6.20		4.10		2.10 "
Hippuric "	6.10		3.87		2.23 "
Oleic "	6.15	6.15	3.57	3.58	2.58 "
Amino-salicylic "	6.15		4.01		2.14 "
Amino-benzoic "	6.00		3.96		2.04 "
Cinnamic "	6.10		3.92		2.18 "

The difference in p_n is increased. It seems that most of the free acid has been washed off and the washing may also be expected to diminish the thickness of the coat. Results of activation, at 250° for 2 hours of the charcoal X, coated with the acids have been given in Tables VIII and IX. The decrease of the p_n persists even after such activation.

TABLE VIII.

Coat of	A_1		A_2		Difference in p_n unit.
	M_1	M_2	M_1	M_2	
Lauric acid	5.85		4.80		1.05 (acid)
Myristic "	6.15		5.41		0.74 "
Palmitic "	5.85	5.83	4.58		1.27 "
Stearic "	6.00		5.02		0.98 "

TABLE IX

Coat of	B ₁		B ₂		Difference in p_H unit
	M ₁	M ₂	M ₁	M ₂	
Lauric acid	6.20	6.18	5.19	5.19	1.01 (acid)
Myristic "	6.25		5.37		0.88 "
Palmitic "	6.20		4.33		1.47 "
Stearic "	6.15		5.09		1.06 "

The coats as prepared by the evaporation on a water-bath may consist of a layer of the organic acid, several molecules thick at places. The activation at 250° ensures that we are dealing with thinner layers or layers present in patches, *i. e.*, which do not cover the whole surface. The extent of the decrease of p_H on the addition of a solution of potassium chloride diminishes on activating the charcoal previously coated with the above acids at 250° for 2 hours and finally the solution turns slightly alkaline on activation at 600° for the same duration (*vide* Table X).

TABLE X.

Coat of	A ₁ M ₁	A ₂ M ₁	Difference in p_H unit.
Lauric acid	6.40	6.69	0.29 (alkali)
Myristic "	6.46	6.67	0.21 "
Palmitic "	6.39	6.69	0.30 "
Stearic "	6.45	6.90	0.45 "

This observation shows that the acidic substances on charcoal surface are gradually decomposed on being activated at a lower temperature, while at a higher temperature they are destroyed as a result of which the charge of the charcoal surface decreases to zero as observed by Roychoudhury (*loc. cit.*). Such a charcoal liberates alkali with neutral salt solution (Roychoudhury and Mukherjee, *loc. cit.*).

Coats of substances other than organic acids.

TABLE XI.

Coat of	A ₁ .		A ₂ .		Difference in p_{H} unit.
	M ₁ .	M ₂ .	M ₁ .	M ₂ .	
Benzyl mercaptan	6.27	6.29	4.29	4.30	1.98 (acid)
Formaldehyde	5.73		4.70		1.03 ..
Acetone	6.00		4.01		1.99 ..
Vaniline	5.12		3.96		1.16 ..

The p_{H} also decreases with coatings of these substances.

It is well known that charcoal holds oxygen very tenaciously. As early as 1867, Calvert (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1867, 29, 293) using comparatively pure charcoal showed the extraordinary activity of the adsorbed oxygen, which took part with ease in many reactions, *e.g.*, the oxidation of ethyl alcohol to acetic acid, while the free gas could not effect it. Later Reed and Wheeler (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1912, 101, 831), Schilov and co-workers (*loc. cit.*, *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1930, 150, 31) and others emphasised the part played by oxygen in the adsorption by charcoal.

It seems that the aldehydes and ketones are oxidised on the charcoal surface to their corresponding acids, by the highly active oxygen, adsorbed on the charcoal and that such of the hydrogen ions of the acids, thus formed, which are present in the mobile sheet of the double layer are easily replaced by cations.

TABLE XII.

Charge measurements.

Treatment of charcoal.	Rate of electro-osmosis (movement of the air bubble in 3 min.).
1. P (activated at 900° for 6 hrs. in air at a pressure of 3 mm. of Hg) in contact with water	0
1(a). P ₁ (obtained by coating P with α -naphthylamine) in contact with water	0
1(b). P ₁ and N/10,000-KCl solution	-2 cm.
2. Q (activated at 600° for 6 hrs. in air at a pressure of 3 mm. Hg) in contact with water	-3.6 cm.
2(a). Q ₁ (obtained by coating Q with α -naphthylamine) in contact with water	-2 cm.
2(b). Q ₁ and N/10,000-KCl solution	-3.0 cm.

TABLE XII (contd.).

Charge measurements

Treatment of charcoal.	Rate of electro-osmosis (movement of the air bubble in 3 min).
3. R (purified by washing but unactivated) in contact with water	- 9.0 cm.
3(a). R ₁ (obtained by coating R with <i>α</i> -naphthylamine) in contact with water	-6.0 cm.
3(b). R ₁ and N/10,000-KCl solution	-1.6 cm.

It appears that on treatment with amine the nature of the surface changes. It develops a capacity to assume a negative charge in contact with the electrolyte presumably by an adsorption of the anion as the electrolyte no longer diminishes the negative charge but increases it. Positive sugar charcoal which has been activated at 900° has a tendency to adsorb chlorine ions (*vide* Roychoudhury, *loc. cit.*). With negatively charged surfaces, the electrical adsorption of the K⁺ ions preponderates. Perhaps the adsorption of chlorine ion is more general and of the nature of a primary adsorption and is further facilitated by the amine ions present on the surface.

TABLE XIII.

Coats of	Amount of amine per g. of charcoal.	A ₁ M ₁ .	A ₂ M ₁ .	Difference in p_H unit.
Diphenylamine	0.01	6.42; 6.42	6.21; 6.21	0.21 (acid)
	0.1 ₂	6.53	6.75	0.22 (alkali)
	0.2	6.62; 6.65	7.01; 7.03	0.38 "
<i>α</i> -Naphthylamine	0.01	6.46	6.39	0.07 (acid)
	0.1	6.57	6.99	0.42 (alkali)
	0.2	6.66; 6.66	7.12; 7.19	0.46 "
Toluenediamine	0.01	6.42	6.56	0.14 "
	0.1	6.58	6.90	0.32 "
Phenylenediamine	0.01	6.40	6.51	0.11 "
	0.1	6.52	6.82	0.30 "

TABLE XIV.

Iso-electric charcoal.
Sample Y.

Coat of	Conc. of KCl	A ₁ . M ₁	A ₂ . M ₁	Difference in p_H unit.
Diphenylamine	0.025 N	6.44; 6.44	6.63; 6.67	0.19 (alkali)
	1.0	„	6.67	0.23 „
	2.0	„	6.69	0.25 „
α-Naphthylamine	0.025 N	6.40; 6.41	6.65	0.15 „
	1.0	„	6.80	0.40 „
	2.0	6.0; 6.41	6.93; 7.01	0.53 „
Toluenediamine	0.025 N	6.57	6.70	0.13 „
	1.0	„	6.93	0.36 „
	2.0	„	7.16	0.59 „

It will be seen from Tables XIII and XIV that the amount of alkali, liberated by potassium chloride solution from the charcoal surface coated with amines, depends on three factors, such as the charge of the charcoal, amount of the amine per g. of charcoal and the concentration of the potassium chloride solution added.

The results obtained in Tables XIII and XIV are easily understood from our observations and from those of Kruyt and Kadt (*Kolloid Beihefte*, 1931, **32**, 249) who have shown that oxygen-free charcoal carries a positive charge which should according to Mukherjee (*loc. cit.*) liberate alkali. The charcoal used in Table XIII, contains some acidic substances on its surface but on treating with increasing amounts of the amines, the proportion of the amine-covered area increases. The surface has possibly a composite character and the acid liberating patches gradually diminish in proportion as the alkali liberating patches increase. Table XIV shows that liberation of the alkali increases with the increase in the concentration of the electrolyte. Since charcoal activated at high temperatures and without an amine coating can liberate alkali, it is not possible to attribute this property solely to the amine. At the same time treatment with the amine appears to favour an increase

in the proportion of such patches or alternatively the diminution of the acid patches. The positive charge observed in several cases as the result of activation at high temperatures seem to suggest that the charcoal surface has a primarily adsorbed layer of cations. Adsorption of hydrogen ions by the weakly basic adsorbed amine groups may be responsible for the formation of the primarily adsorbed cation layer which gives a positive charge to the surface and leads to a liberation of the electrically adsorbed or mobile hydroxyl ions on addition of neutral salts.

S U M M A R Y .

1. Coats of different insoluble organic substances have been formed from their alcoholic solutions on activated sugar charcoal and their properties have been studied with respect to their surface charge and the liberation of acid or alkali by neutral salt solutions.

2. The acid coats increase the surface negative charge, which diminishes on being treated with neutral salt solutions in the order $KCl > NaCl > LiCl > BaCl_2$.

3. Acid is liberated from the acid coats by neutral salt solutions in the order corresponding with their capacity to diminish the surface negative charge, $KCl > NaCl > LiCl > RbCl > SrCl_2 > BaCl_2$.

4. Activation of the coated charcoal diminishes the amount of acid liberated.

5. Similar acid liberating coats can also be obtained with mercaptan, aldehyde and ketones.

6. Amine coats diminishes the surface negative charge, which increases on being treated with neutral salt solutions. Alkali is liberated from amine coats by neutral salt solution and the amount depends on the initial charge of the charcoal, the concentration of the neutral salt solution and the amount of amine per g. of charcoal.

My best thanks are due to Prof. J. N. Mukherjee for suggesting this work and for facilities.